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Effect of organic manures on some predators in the rice ecosystem

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We studied the effect of organic manures on some predators in field trials at the Agricultural College and Research Institute, Killikulam, in southern Tamil Nadu under lowland irrigated conditions. ASD16, a popular rice variety, was planted at 10- × 8-cm spacing. Plot size was 10 × 2 m². Trials were laid out in a randomized block design with five treatments: T1—farmyard manure (FYM), T2—FYM + neem cake, T3—FYM + *Azolla*, T4—FYM + neem cake + *Azolla*, and FYM + NPK as the control. In all treatments, FYM at 12.5 t ha⁻¹ was applied basally. Neem cake was applied at 1.5 t ha⁻¹. *Azolla* was applied 20 d after transplanting and allowed to multiply for about 15–20 d. Visual counts m² were made on some common predators such as ground beetle

(*Ophionea* sp.), rove beetle (*Paederus* sp.), coccinellid beetle, and spiders (per m² area) at early tillering, active tillering, and maximum tillering stages.

Results showed that the predator population was higher in plots with *Azolla*, with or without neem cake (see table). The mean predator population of *Ophionea indica*, *Paederus fuscipes*, coccinellid beetles, and *Lycosa* sp. was significantly higher in *Azolla*-applied plots. The *Azolla* mat on the water may have provided a favorable niche for colonization of beetles and spiders. The higher number of predators may have helped control rice pests, including stem borer larvae (Reissig et al 1986, Raguraman and Rajasekaran 1996). Early instar stem borer larvae that

disperse may fall prey to any of these active predators. *Azolla* cover may hamper the exit of migrating larvae that make a window on the internodes, mostly at the base. The possible effect on the stem borer population, however, requires further study.

References

- Raguraman S, Rajasekaran B. 1996. Effect of neem products on insect pests of rice and the predatory spider. *Madras Agric. J.* 83(8):510–515.
- Reissig WH, Heinrichs EA, Litsinger JA, Moody K, Fielder L, Mew TW, Barrion AT. 1986. Illustrated guide to integrated pest management in rice in tropical Asia. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. 411 p.

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Treatment	Mean (± SE) no. of insects m ⁻²				
	<i>Ophionea indica</i>	<i>Paederus fuscipes</i>	Coccinellid beetles	<i>Lycosa</i> sp.	<i>Tetragnatha</i> sp.
T1—FYM at 12.5 t ha ⁻¹	600.0 ± 0.1 (2.55) bc	1.7 ± 0.1 (1.47) c	6.0 ± 1.0 (2.55) b	5.0 ± 0.5 (2.34) b	0.7 ± 0.1 (1.08) a
T2—FYM at 12.5 t ha ⁻¹ + neem cake (NC) at 1.5 t ha ⁻¹	400.0 ± 0.4 (2.12) c	1.3 ± 0.3 (1.35) c	6.3 ± 0.8 (2.61) b	5.7 ± 0.2 (2.48) b	0.7 ± 0.3 (1.08) a
T3—FYM at 12.5 t ha ⁻¹ + <i>Azolla</i> at 5 t ha ⁻¹	16.7 ± 0.4 (2.12) a	5.3 ± 0.3 (2.42) ab	14.7 ± 0.3 (3.89) a	8.0 ± 0.4 (2.92) a	1.7 ± 0.1 (1.47) a
T4—FYM at 12.5 t ha ⁻¹ + NC at 1.5 t ha ⁻¹ + <i>Azolla</i> at 5 t ha ⁻¹	15.7 ± 0.7 (4.02) a	6.7 ± 0.8 (2.68) a	12.3 ± 0.3 (3.58) a	8.3 ± 0.9 (2.97) a	1.7 ± 0.1 (1.47) a
Control—FYM at 12.5 t ha ⁻¹ + NPK at 150:50:50 kg ha ⁻¹	10.0 ± 0.4 (3.24) b	3.7 ± 0.4 (2.06) b	8.0 ± 0.4 (2.92) b	7.0 ± 0.3 (2.74) a	2.3 ± 0.2 (1.68) a
Mean	10.4 ± 0.4 (3.31)	3.7 ± 0.3 (2.06)	9.5 ± 0.3 (3.16)	6.8 ± 0.03 (2.70)	1.4 ± 0.3 (1.38)

^aMean of three replications, numbers in parentheses are square roots of (x + 0.5) – transformed values. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.